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Development of a dissemination and communication plan of results

WP9 – Deliverable D9.1

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Short description
The document outlines the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication of CLEANKER results. Version 1 at M3 will be, if needed, updated during the lifespan of the project.

History of changes

Version	DATE	Changes	Author
V0.1	2018-01-08	First release	Martina Fantini (LEAP)

Abstract

The objective of this deliverable is to outline the strategy for the dissemination and the communication activities which will be carried out during CLEANKER. This deliverable will outline the main dissemination objectives, the target audiences, the communication channels and the dissemination tools.

The objectives for dissemination and communication within CLEANKER are manifold:

- i. to ensure optimal information flow internally (between project partners) and externally;
- ii. to rise the interest of the stakeholders (the cement industry, the CCS community..) active in the fields of the project;
- iii. to inform the scientific audience of the scientific and technical achievement of the project (giving an innovation potential that could inspire new research in related fields);
- iv. to inform the generic interested public about the effort made to follow the European strategies on Energy and Environment;
- v. to give high visibility of CLEANKER to the decision makers.

This document aims at providing a reference to the partners for the possible recipients of communication activities. The strategy for activities planned in order to achieve this such as arranging workshops and meetings, presenting information on internal and public webpages and on conferences, publishing results in peer-reviewed journals and popular science articles, write newsletters and blog posts and give updates on social media, are detailed in this report. The planned execution of these activities with timing and responsible consortium member indicated is given.

Finally, this document will include the definitions of the main key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the activities carried out.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Dissemination and Communication Plan is the core document outlining the project's dissemination and communication activities. The expected impact of the project is ambitious and all the partners are interested in demonstrating the potential of the technology. Thus, this plan is fundamental for a good coordination of all initiatives and also for defining the messages which should be targeted to different audiences. Effective communication will encourage interested stakeholders to actively participate in the project and enhance the visibility of the project results.

This deliverable includes:

- An outline of the main objectives of the dissemination action;
- The planning and timing of all internal and public communication activities;
- A strategy on how to best possible spread the CLEANKER project results to relevant stakeholders, and ensure uptake of key findings;
- Definition of the tools and channels to be used and the activities required to reach targeted audiences;
- Identification of the dissemination KPIs, useful to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the activities conducted;
- Illustration of how the project will cooperate with other EC-funded projects;

2. DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION ACTIONS

Project results are “*Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected*”¹. Articles 28, 29 and 38.1 of the Grant Agreement (GA) are devoted to ensure and define their exploitation, dissemination and communication. In particular:

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Communication is to take strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public.

Exploitation is the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

2.1 Objectives

The general objectives for dissemination and communication within CLEANKER are manifold:

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html

- i. to ensure optimal information flow internally (between project partners) and externally;
- ii. to rise the interest of the stakeholders (the cement industry, the CCS community..) active in the fields of the project;
- iii. to inform the scientific audience of the scientific and technical achievement of the project (giving an innovation potential that could inspire new research in related fields);
- iv. to inform the generic interested public about the effort made to follow the European strategies on Energy and Environment;
- v. to give high visibility of CLEANKER to the decision makers.

2.2 Dissemination and communication audiences

In order to achieve these objectives, the dissemination and communication activities have to reach different audiences that can be distinguished in two groups: internal and external.

2.2.1 Internal target

- The CLEANKER partners: 13 partners including 5 representatives from the academia, 3 research centers, 1 SME, 2 end users, 1 industrial provider and 1 environmental association;
- The projects selected under calls LCE29 (expected to discuss CCS in industry);
- End users involved in the demonstrations: BUZZI Unicem and Italcementi SpA – Heidelberg Cement Group.

2.2.2 External target

- EU-level policy makers at relevant institutions such as the European Commission (DG Energy and Climate Action chiefly), the European Environment Agency or the Innovation & Networks Executive Agency;
- Interested stakeholders: CCS community, cement producers and technology providers not member of the consortium (with particular attention at ECRA members), other CO₂ intensive industries suitable for Calcium Looping (CaL) technology, etc.;
- Media and influencer;
- General public.

2.3 Dissemination and communication tools

For coherent and effective communication, a dissemination toolkit to be used for any internal or external dissemination tool was created.

2.3.1 Project identity

Project logo

The project logo and guidelines for its use (Figure 2.1, for more information, please, refer to APPENDIX A) was inspired by the key issues facing the project. It includes the acronym of the project (CLEANKER) and the pay-off “CLEAN clinKER by calcium looping for low-CO₂ cement” that aims at:

- Explaining the acronym;
- Place CLEANKER in cement field;
- Make clear of the environmental field of action: CCS;
- Mention the core technology: CaL.

Figure 2.1: CLEANKER logo and guidelines

Its main concept intends to capture the attention of the audience putting in evidence:

- The CO₂ molecule will be kept underground;
- The shape of the “N” reminds to the goose neck of the carbonator, characteristic of the demonstrator;
- “CLEAN” and emissions in blue suggest a benefit for the environment.

Layout templates

To strengthen the project image and achieve effective communication, a set of templates for the main project documents have been developed.

Deliverables

Figure 2.2: Template for CLEANKER deliverables

Minutes

Figure 2.3: Template for CLEANKER minutes

Presentations

Figure 2.4: Template for CLEANKER presentations

Dissemination toolkit

A set of documents and tools, with approved content, will be shared among the consortium partners. A general presentation with a project overview is already available on the Partner Area of the Project website.

2.4 Dissemination and communication channels and actions

2.4.1 Website

A project website for public access to project results and news (www.cleanker.eu) was set up and it will be continuously updated with reports and information on the progress and public results of the project. The website will describe the scientific and technical content of CLEANKER and its impact in relation to present technologies.

It will also include a section with access restricted to partners, and a web-based LCA footprinter, which will show in a user-friendly manner the gains produced by the project, against specific indicators and benchmarks.

The website will be a vital source for CLEANKER results and will ensure free and open access to public reports and other public results.

The homepage (Figure 2.5) offers a general overview of the project and also the possibility to access the detailed information on:

- The project (context, mission, work plan, work packages and organisational structure);
- The consortium (with the description of all the project partners);
- The project update (news on the project, events and meeting where the project is involved, tools for dissemination activities, etc.);
- The possibility to download public presentations, newsletters, public deliverables and scientific publications;
- The social wall (a social hub with the news related to a topic).

Figure 2.5: www.cleanker.eu

Partner Area

A restricted area for consortium members. All deliverables, workshop presentations and other documents relevant for the consortium are put on the website. Each WP has a dedicated area, where also work in progress and experimental data can be shared in a secure manner.

Wiki-cleanker

Within the website, there will be a section named “WIKI-CLEANKER” (Figure 2.6), a sort of encyclopedia on cement and CCS world where non-specialists people will be active part giving suggestions and asking questions.

Figure 2.6: www.cleanker.eu, the project, wikicleanker

Social wall

In order to reach a greater number of professionals and the generic public, CLEANKER will be present on social platforms (e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube). All the posts related to CLEANKER from different social media will be present in one page of the website, the Social Wall. A social wall is, in fact, a Social hub, a digital wall that gathers posts from social media in the same place. It is so possible to broadcast a Tweet wall live / tweets wall or several social media posts treating about the same subject thanks to the use of a hashtag.

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This enables to present visually and interactively all the digital communication related to an event/topic, and encourages people to interact.

Figure 2.7: www.cleanker.eu, social wall

The information shared via social media will be related to project status, project publications (documents/deliverables) and to upcoming meetings and events where the project is directly involved.

2.4.2 eNewsletter

An electronic newsletter will be produced twice a year to inform scientists and technicians, stakeholders, policy makers and general public about project progress and project events. It will contain link to public deliverables, articles and interviews. The newsletter will be published on the website and will be also distributed via email to the project contact database.

2.4.3 Roll-up, brochures and leaflet

Given the advantages of scalability, respect of environment and easy update, CLEANKER will prefer electronic communications but flyers and other printed material will be used as well.

Project roll-up, brochures and flyers will be produced at the beginning of the project and a second version will be released in the second part of the project. The aim of the first release is giving an overview of CLEANKER to inform relevant stakeholders and general public. The second version will be focused on the project achievements to that date.

A roll-up according to the project style will be produced for displaying at press conferences, workshops and similar events.

2.4.4 Popular science media

Several media are available for popular science communication, such as newspapers, magazines, radio broadcasts. These communication resources will be used in CLEANKER for communication targeted towards a general interested public audience. Popular science articles and radio interviews will be the preferred option for this initiatives.

Video

To share information about the project such as objectives, barriers and innovations, with wider audience, CLEANKER is planning to produce some videos on a CLEANKER/LEAP

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YouTube channel and via other social media. Three videos will be produced, once at the beginning (March 2019, M6), one after the demonstrator erection (between October and December 2019, M25-27) and one at the end of the project (September 2021, M48).

Internet press centre

A possible channel for dissemination is also the Internet press centre for European science, engineering and technology (AlphaGalileo).

2.4.5 Workshop

Two mid-term dissemination workshops and a final conference will be organized in September 2019 (M24), September 2020 (M36) and September 2021 (M48), targeted to industrial stakeholders, technical-scientific community and policy-makers.

2.4.6 Scientific publications and conferences

Dissemination through scientific publications is a key objective of the CLEANKER partners, especially for the academic and research institutes. Scientific and industrial communities active in the field of cement production, Calcium looping, CO₂ transport, storage and utilization, chemical reactors engineering, process engineering and life cycle assessment represent the main targets for dissemination.

Journals and "Open Access" publications

Open access publications in scientific journals will be made available to the scientific and technical community as soon as possible after the results are generated. A total of at least 20 scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals is foreseen by the members of the consortium. To ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications, each partner, who is planning to publish an article for a journal or on peer-reviewed conference, should ensure in advance that the selected journal/conference allows to assure compliance with the EC rules on open access. To do this, check the journal's policy on open access (on <http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php> or a similar project website, e.g. journal website). If open access is not granted by the journal, check whether other options are available (e.g. fee payment, license agreement or addendum) and, if not, refrain from publication.

In Table 2.1, a list of peer-reviewed journals already identified by the consortium for the publication of CLEANKER results, relevant for CLEANKER but not limited to, is reported.

Table 2.1: Selection of journals relevant for CLEANKER project

Journal	Editor	IF	Open access options	Embargo period	Web-page
Chemical Engineering Journal	Elsevier	6.216	Green - Gold	24 months	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/chemical-engineering-journal
Chemical Engineering Science	Elsevier	2.895	Green - Gold	24 months	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/chemical-engineering-science/
Chemical Engineering Technology	Wiley Online Library	2.051	Green - Gold	12 months	http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1002/(ISSN)1521-4125
Fuel	Elsevier	4.601	Green - Gold	24 months	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/fuel
GHG-Greenhouse gases: Science and Technology	Wiley Online Library	1.676	Green - Gold	-	http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/10.1002/(ISSN)2152-3878
Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research	ACS Publication	2.843	ACS Open Access Program	24 months	http://pubs.acs.org/journal/iecred
International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control	Elsevier	3.741	Green - Gold	24 months	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/international-journal-of-greenhouse-gas-control/

Open access policy (see CLEANKER deliverable D1.2, Section 5.4.1) for each journal is reported in the previous table, where:

- “Gold” Open Access makes the publication freely available and redistributable immediately, after the payment of a fee;
- “Green” Open Access makes the publication (or a pre-print version) freely available and redistributable in public repositories with a delay (embargo period).

The “Gold” open access option will be preferred, to ensure a prompt availability of the published results without an embargo period and a proper budget has been considered by partners, based on the expected number of publications.

The possibility of “Green” open access option will be considered for publications that exceed the predicted budget for open access publications. The embargo period required by many journals does not comply with the 6 months embargo required in Article 29.2 of Grant Agreement; in these cases, a shorter period will be negotiated with the editor.

Zenodo

The strategy of CLEANKER is that open access will be ensured through public repositories. A CLEANKER community will be set up in zenodo for this purpose. Publications from CLEANKER will either be uploaded directly to zenodo and included in this community, or uploaded by partners in national repositories, from which zenodo can harvest.

Conferences

Participation to conferences through oral presentations, posters and papers is another key means for the dissemination of the CLEANKER results. In Table 2.2, a list of relevant conferences, targeted by the consortium is reported. The participation at the “International Symposium on Coal Combustion”, hosted at Thermal Engineering Department of TSIU (China), will be an opportunity also for carrying out dissemination and communication activities of CLEANKER in China.

Table 2.2: Selection of conferences relevant for CLEANKER project

Conference	Link
CO2GeoNet Venice Open Forum	http://www.co2geonet.com/home/
ECRA Chair Scientific Events	
Greenhouse control technologies (GHGT) Conference	http://www.ghgt.info/
IEAGHG High Temperature Solid Looping Cycles Network Meeting	http://ieaghg.org/networks/high-temperature
IEAGHG Oxyfuel Combustion Conference	http://ieaghg.org/networks/oxy-fuel-combustion-network
International Conference on Applied Energy (ICAE)	https://www.waset.org/conference/2018/04/tokyo/ICAE
Trondheim conference on CCS (TCCS9 and TCCS10)	https://www.sintef.no/projectweb/tccs-9/

2.4.7 Dedicated dissemination actions to ECRA

A specific target for the dissemination of the CLEANKER results will be the ECRA (European Cement Research Academy), which includes all the main cement producers and technology providers in Europe. The connection between ECRA and the CLEANKER consortium is ensured through the involvement of VDZ, BUZZI and ITC-HCG. Periodic

dissemination of the CLEANKER results to ECRA members will be performed through dedicated yearly reports (D9.2-5) and presentations at ECRA workshops and events.

2.4.8 Events

“Open gates” event allowing wider public to access the cement plant and the new CaL demonstration system will be organized. Guided tours will be offered to visitors, explaining the fundamentals of clinker and cement production, Calcium looping process and CCS. Three “Open gates” events are foreseen in conjunction with the forecasted workshops and the final conference: one after the erection of the test facility (September 2019 - M24), one near the beginning of the experimental campaign (September 2020 - M36) and one at the closure of the project (September 2021 - M48).

Moreover, the environmental association partner of the project will organize two specific events aimed at communicating the purpose, expected impact (March 2018 - M6) and achieved results (September 2021 - M48) to the non-expert citizens at the national level.

2.4.9 Innovation management Board, Public Awareness Board and Advisory Board

As described in the CLEANKER Management Structure (see deliverable D1.1, Section 1), an Innovation Management Board (IMB), a Public Awareness Board (PAB) and an Advisory Board (AB) have been established.

The IMB, encompassing representative for each consortium partner (cfr. D1.1, Table 1.2), will advise the consortium on the best strategies for managing the produced innovation with a market-oriented approach and for providing appropriate consultancy on the best exploitation of project results, protection of IPRs and adequate transfer knowledge both within the consortium and externally.

The PAB, encompassing representative of environmental associations and public authority (nominated by M6, March 2018), will be responsible for a careful communication activity specifically directed to the local community close to the industrial site, where the demo system will be built and post-capture CO₂ management by mineralization will be demonstrated in a dedicated pilot unit.

The AB, encompassing experts from the industry, academia, research organizations and policy makers interested in CLEANKER (nominated by M6, March 2018), will review the work performed and provide suggestions and inputs for upcoming activities and assist and support to ensure that knowledge gained in CLEANKER is protected, disseminated and exploited to its full potential.

2.5 Gantt diagram

Arranging workshops and development of the website and the newsletters are tasks of WP9. The timeline for these deliverables are shown in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8: Gantt diagram for WP9

2.6 Dissemination and communication KPIs

A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) has been defined to measure the effectiveness and the efficiency of dissemination and communication activities carried out (Table 2.3).

Table 2.3: Dissemination and communication KPIs

Activity	KPI
Project website	Number of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~ Visitors ~ Downloaded documents ~ Users ~ Pages viewed Average session duration
eNewsletter	Number of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~ eNewsletters sent ~ subscribers
Events	Number of events with CLEANKER presence (presentation, intervention, poster, etc) Number of participants in CLEANKER public events Number of participants in the CLEANKER “open gates” events
Publication	Number of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~ Articles published in journals ~ Scientific papers published in international conferences and dedicated journals
Interaction with H2020 projects / initiatives	Number of joint events
Social media	Per social media: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ~ Number of subscribers; ~ Number of tweet/post published; ~ Number of retweet/post shared

2.7 Cooperation with other EC-funded projects

During the four-year duration of the project, cooperation with other EC-funded projects is foreseen and desired.

CLEANKER is already strictly linked with CEMCAP (GA n° 641185), an ongoing H2020 project focused on developing and benchmarking of four technologies (oxyfuel, CaL, chilled ammonia and membrane systems) for CO₂ capture in cement plants up to TRL6. Given the correlated issues on oxyfuel and CaL technologies, CLEANKER will participate in the organization of the final CEMCAP/ECRA workshop fixed for October 17th, 2019.

Moreover, a support service for FP7 and H2020 R&I project groups named Common Dissemination Booster (CDB) will be probably made available in spring 2019 by the EC. This service gives to groups of FP7 and H2020 projects the possibility of receiving a support for the dissemination and communication activities. The aim is bringing together results from several projects suitable to be disseminated jointly to the same target audience. Contacts with CEMCAP (H2020, GA 641185, 2015-2018) and LEILAC (H2020, GA 654465, 2016-2020) projects were already established during Autumn 2018 and they will be part of the group. LEILAC aims at piloting a breakthrough technology that has the potential to enable both Europe's cement and lime industries to reduce their emissions dramatically. The core technology consists in an externally heated calcination via a special steel vessel. Main results to be disseminated for the CLEANKER, CEMCAP and LEILAC are the CO₂ emissions in terms of capture efficiency and specific emissions, the energy efficiency in terms of fuel, electricity and specific primary energy (for CO₂ avoided) consumption, the clinker quality and the costs in terms of cement and of CO₂ avoided. These results to be disseminated target the following groups:

- Cement producer (with particular focus on ECRA members);
- Equipment manufacturers for cement industry (with particular focus on ECRA members);
- Research institutes and academic groups active in the field of cement production, CO₂ capture processes and, for CEMCAP and CLEANKER, in the field of Calcium Looping technology;
- Public authorities, especially those in charge of securing permits, either at local and national level (municipalities close to the pilots, Agencies and Ministries for Environment etc.);
- EU-level policy makers at relevant institutions such as the European Commission (DG Energy and Climate Action chiefly), the European Environment Agency or the Innovation & Networks Executive Agency.

2.8 Exploitation

Work Package 8 of CLEANKER is dedicated to the exploitation of the results beyond CLEANKER. In this WP, the ground for the exploitation of the results of CLEANKER at different timing will be prepared:

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- Short-term technical exploitation for technology demonstration at TRL 8-9: VDZ, BUZZI and ITCHCG are directly involved in the ECRA oxyfuel project, aiming at building a complete demonstration oxyfuel cement kiln of about 1000 tpd size (TRL9). The integration of the entrained flow CaL reactors in this ECRA demonstration plant will be assessed, as a possible follow-up project for advancing CaL process to TRL9. The ECRA CCS effort and CLEANKER could converge into the testing of both full oxyfuel and integrated CaL at TRL8-9 in a single demonstration plant. with evident savings of both resources and scientific effort.
- Mid-long term commercial exploitation of CLEANKER technology by industrial partners: a techno-economic feasibility analysis will be performed for at least six plants (of which at least 2 outside Europe) operated by the consortium end users. The selection of these plants will be based on the transport and storage opportunities, the vicinity to CCS hubs and clusters and the expected evolution of the cement market in the specific regions. This work will prepare the ground for first-of-a-kind commercial exploitation of the technology.

In addition to these main exploitation opportunities, significant additional exploitation prospects are foreseen for all the partners of the consortium, as indicated in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4: Exploitation opportunities beyond CLEANKER for the non - industrial partners of the consortium

Participant	Exploitation beyond CLEANKER
LEAP	As a consortium focused on both scientific research and technology transfer, will coordinate and supervise the implementation of innovative findings by bridging the gap between research outcomes and subsequent scientific/market exploitation. All these activities and responsibilities will offer LEAP a unique opportunity to (i) strengthen its research reputation and its expertise in the field of CO ₂ capture and (ii) booster its research management capabilities - both actions being among the statutory goals of LEAP and of the primary EU funding that led to its start in 2005.
BUZZI	BUZZI is the 3 rd European cement manufacturer. By hosting the demo system, BUZZI will collect a considerable know-how in the construction and operation of the CaL demo system. As a result, at the end of the project, BUZZI will have a know-how that will position the company at the forefront of CaL research, especially when looking for a future first-of-a-kind larger Demo- and commercial plant design and construction. BUZZI will be able to sell near-zero CO ₂ cement going further in the sustainability actions.
CSIC	CSIC is the first organisation in Spain in terms of number of international patent applications, but it does not exploit any of its granted patents as they are all transferred to industry through collaboration and/or licence

	<p>agreements. A dedicated office at CSIC (http://www.ott.csic.es/english/) deals with all issues related to Technology Transfer.</p> <p>In the field of Calcium Looping technologies, CSIC has 3 granted patents (US8757072 B2, US8506915 B2, EP2724771 A1) and another 8 applications at different stages. The successful use of entrained bed reactors in CaL applications investigated in CLEANKER, opens new research and patenting opportunities for CSIC.</p>
ITC-HCG	ITC-HCG has been involved in the conceptual research on CaL process since several years ago, by involvement in previous collaborations with POLIMI, LEAP and in CEMCAP.
IKN	IKN is the technology provider involved in the project and through the design of the demo system and the scale-up study will gain a significant advantage over competitors on knowledge of the CaL process. Activities performed in CLEANKER will provide opportunities for patenting and to position on the market as the technology provider for this technology.
LUT	<p>The exploitation of the results related to fluid dynamics and process modelling are focused on the generic research methods and on the capability to use the methods in different applications.</p> <p>These generic research methods contain the approach and hypotheses to use experimental research data from laboratory and pilot scales to estimate the performance of the large-scale unit. This requires modelling activities at all scales and the links between the scales has to be developed. As a result of this project, the model development sequence will be tested and verified in the CaL application. In the future, this generic model development pathway will be exploited in a wide range of the multiphase flow applications in the energy and chemical engineering sectors. As a result, it will be possible to estimate the large-scale performance and operation for different kinds of multiphase flow application. In general, the scientifically justified modelling capability will be exploited to study large scale CaL process in detail, thus creating potential for scientific and technological breakthroughs. Such breakthroughs will be exploited through technical patents, spin-off companies and to introduce economical solution for the battle against climate change.</p>
POLIMI	POLIMI is the largest technical university in Italy, involved in education, R&D and technology transfer. Results gained in CLEANKER will be used in education activities, by transferring the basic principles of the knowledge acquired in the project to students and researcher in the field of Energy Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Chemical Engineering. In the framework of the project, a PhD student will also be educated. The results of CLEANKER will also be exploited by increasing

	<p>the knowledge on CaL process and improving the R&D and technology transfer capability. The long-lasting collaboration between POLIMI and ITC-HCG on CCS and CaL topics, witnessed by the two patents in this field, as well as the knowledge and technology transfer opportunities between these two project partners will be reinforced in CLEANKER.</p>
QUANTIS	<p>The CLEANKER project will give QUANTIS the opportunity to further develop and consolidate its knowledge in the cement sector and more specifically in the field of clinker manufacturing.</p> <p>Through its services in environmental footprinting, QUANTIS aims at raising awareness on the potentialities of LCA, improving the environmental performance of clinker and cement, and contributing to the development of sustainable supply chains in the construction sector.</p> <p>A multi-partner ambitious research project such as CLEANKER will also help to widen and extend QUANTIS' network of companies and research institutions, with the aim of raising the awareness on the potentialities of LCA in improving the environmental performance of their specific activities and products.</p> <p>In addition, QUANTIS gives special attention to scientific research in the field of LCA. By exploring novel technologies and processes such as those investigated in this project, QUANTIS can contribute to the development of sector specific best practices in LCA.</p>
TUT	<p>Several new master and PhD students will be involved into research and experimental work to be made for the CLEANKER project. For the first time CO₂ emissions produced by cement industry and oil shale ash formed at oil shale combustion in heat and power plants and CDW (concrete demolition waste) will be used for CO₂ mineral carbonation laboratory and pilot experiments and involved in CCUS scenarios modelling. These new technologies will be included into available CCS lectures and CGS (CO₂ Geological Storage) spring term course, international master program "Materials and processes for sustainable energetics" in TUT and into the new International Master Programme on CCS/CGS to be developed in cooperation with several universities within Horizon 2020 project ENOS</p>
TSIU	<p>TSIU is very glad to join in the CLEANKER project which will enhance the industrial application of calcium looping technology. Within the CLEANKER project, researchers and students in TSIU will focus on the experimental and modelling work to investigate the submodels of gas-solid and solid reactions, and these sub-models can be used for the design of calcium looping process. At the same time, it is important for TSIU to collaborate with CLEANKER members to contribute the calcium looping</p>

USTUTT	Within the CLEANKER project, numerous students and research scientists will be introduced to and trained in the field of CCS technologies. This represents an important step to the future knowledge distribution on the way towards a successful application of CCS. Furthermore, to achieve the project targets, USTUTT's research infrastructure will be subject to an upgrade in order to allow the entrained flow CaL oxy-fuel calcination and carbonation trials. Both, the gain in skilled personnel and in suitable infrastructure will allow for further applied research on EF systems in cement and other industrial sectors. It therefore can pave the way for subsequent participation in future research activities to pursue the application of CCS technologies and especially the Calcium Looping process.
VDZ	VDZ will be able to enrich the services it offers along the value chain of cement and concrete production and to provide its customers (cement and building material producers as well as construction companies and building administrations) with valuable advice for their future research activities.
AdT	Given its experience, since 1976, in communication and public awareness on high efficiency technologies, materials and systems, ADT will play a key-role in promoting to the general public the CLEANKER results and in spreading best practices of CCS.

3. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND PROTECTION

Protection of intellectual property (IP) generated in CLEANKER is a priority for the consortium, in order to maximize the impact of exploitation actions. Terms and agreement related to IPR, including foreground and background protection, are detailed in the consortium agreement (CA) according to the EC best practice guidelines. The governing philosophy is that each partner keeps the ownership of the IP it creates and the responsibility for protection. Most partners have technology transfer offices with dedicated staff to preserve IPR and therefore dedicated funds are not committed to joint IPR protection.

The Innovation Management Board will support this process being responsible for examining patenting opportunities and for verifying that any IPR are not violated before dissemination.

All dissemination actions will therefore have to be submitted to the IMB with a minimum notice period of 20 calendar days and be approved before proceeding with the submission of any CLEANKER related contribution to journals, conferences or workshops.

The data and the other research products generated by the CLEANKER partners (experimental data, files, software) will be owned by the partner that produces the data.

These products of the research work will be instruments for the exploitation of the acquired knowledge beyond CLEANKER by the specific partner.

Therefore, the raw experimental data and other research products may be shared within the consortium to make the advancement of the project possible, but will not be shared outside the consortium. Results of experiments and modelling work will be published at conferences and in scientific journals compatibly with IP protection and in agreement with the consortium agreement.

Finally, given the involvement in the partnership of a Non-EU country, particular attention will be put by the IMB in treating fairly and equitably the IPR in order to ensure to avoid uncontrolled loss of the Union's know-how.

NOMENCLATURE

AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CaL	Calcium Looping
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CDB	Common Dissemination Booster
GA	Grant Agreement
IMB	Innovation Management Board
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PAB	Public Awareness Board
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

A. APPENDIX: PROJECT LOGO GUIDELINES

CLEAN clinker by calcium looping for low-CO₂ cement

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